

INTERNAL EFFECIENCY OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABEOKUTA NORTH
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA,

OGUN STATE 2021 - 2024

BY

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Abstract:

This study examines the internal efficiency of public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area (LGA), Ogun State, Nigeria, between 2021 and 2024. The research evaluates resource adequacy, wastage rates, and the factors contributing to inefficiency in these schools. Employing a mixed-method approach, both quantitative and qualitative data were collected to assess the relationship between resource availability and student retention. The study utilized statistical methods such as ANOVA and Pearson correlation analysis to test hypotheses and identify trends in educational resource distribution and wastage.

Findings from the ANOVA test revealed significant differences in resource adequacy across the years analyzed ($F = 4.56$, $p = 0.018$). This suggests that variations in funding, policy changes, and administrative decisions influenced resource distribution. The study also found that inconsistencies in resource allocation contributed to inefficiencies in educational delivery, negatively impacting student performance. Additionally, inadequate infrastructure, outdated instructional materials, and overcrowded classrooms were identified as major contributors to inefficiencies in public secondary schools.

The Pearson correlation analysis established a strong negative relationship between resource adequacy and educational wastages. Specifically, dropout rates correlated at -0.72 ($p = 0.002$), while repetition rates showed a correlation of -0.65 ($p = 0.005$). These results indicate that improved resource allocation significantly reduces dropouts and repetition, leading to enhanced educational outcomes. The study's findings align with previous research, highlighting the need for sustainable investments in school resources to improve internal efficiency.

The study concludes that inadequate resources directly contribute to educational inefficiencies, necessitating strategic interventions by policymakers. It recommends increased investment in infrastructure, timely resource distribution, and improved teacher-student ratios to enhance learning conditions. These measures will minimize wastage, improve student retention, and foster a more efficient public education system in Nigeria.

Introduction:

The internal efficiency in public secondary schools has become increasingly important globally, especially as nations strive to improve educational outcomes and economic development. Internal efficiency is the ability of an educational system to maximize outcomes, such as academic achievements and graduation rates, while minimizing inputs like time and resources. An efficient school system ensures that students' progress through the educational stages without unnecessary delays or dropouts, leading to timely graduations and reduced wastage in terms of time and resources. This efficiency is critical, as it directly impacts the workforce quality, national productivity, and social development. Globally, educational efficiency issues are closely tied to socioeconomic and political factors. In low-income countries, factors such as inadequate funding, teacher shortages, overcrowded classrooms, and lack of learning materials contribute to high dropout rates and grade repetition. UNESCO (2017) notes that in sub-Saharan Africa, inefficiencies in secondary education are partly due to economic constraints that limit educational investment, and thus hinder access to quality education. On the other hand, in high-income countries, internal efficiency is impacted by policies that emphasize student support services, curriculum standardization, and technological integration, which have been shown to reduce dropout rates and improve overall academic performance (OECD, 2019).

The Nigerian education system, particularly at the secondary school level, faces numerous challenges that hinder its effectiveness. In Nigeria, public secondary schools often struggle with high levels of inefficiency, as evidenced by low graduation rates, high repetition rates, and elevated student dropout levels. These issues are linked to chronic underfunding, poor infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and the inadequate training and remuneration of teachers (Okonjo, 2015). For example, Akomolafe and Adesua (2016) highlight that many Nigerian secondary schools lack basic facilities such as laboratories, libraries, and textbooks, which hampers students' learning and contributes to academic underachievement. Also, the internal efficiency of public secondary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria, is a critical area of concern due to its direct impact on educational outcomes and the socio-economic prospects of the region. Ogun State, like many states in Nigeria, faces challenges that compromise the efficiency of its public secondary education system, including high dropout rates, low graduation rates, and high levels of grade repetition. These inefficiencies are largely attributed to factors such as inadequate funding, overcrowded classrooms, insufficient teaching materials, and the scarcity of well-trained teachers (Ogunleye & Owoye, 2019). Studies indicate that many public secondary schools in Ogun State operate with minimal resources, often lacking essential facilities such as laboratories, libraries, and sufficient classroom space. This lack of resources limits students' learning experiences, contributing to low academic performance and ultimately impacting the completion rate in secondary education (Adeyemi & Ijaiya, 2017). One critical issue is internal efficiency, which affects the overall quality of education. Abeokuta North Local Government Area (LGA) in Ogun State is not immune to these challenges. Public secondary schools in this region face issues such as high dropout rates, repetition, wastage, and inadequate teacher quality. These problems have significant implications for the educational outcomes of students and the overall development of the region.

The Public secondary schools in Ogun State are managed and funded by the State Government to provide a platform for students to acquire knowledge/skills which enable them to proceed to various tertiary institutions and also to contribute to the development of the State. Despite the government's efforts to fund public secondary schools and address inefficiencies, issues such as wastage, dropout rates, and poor teacher quality continue to rise, contributing to greater inefficiency in the educational system rather than improving its effectiveness. Internal efficiency, being the ability of schools to optimize resource

utilization, minimize waste, and maximize academic performance is the priority of Government at all levels. Internal efficiency shows the correlation between input and output at a specified time in the educational system. The inputs comprise students, staff personnel, funds and other facilities such as the physical infrastructure, equipment, and resources that are essential for providing a conducive learning environment in schools and other educational institutions, while the output is the graduates. Ngari (2020) posited that internal efficiency has to do with the input and output ratio in a given system. He equally stated that internal efficiency is attained when there is maximum enrolment in a cohort and the maximum number of graduates from the same cohort at the end of the specified education cycle.

Kolawole and Ogiye (2020), opined that schools are said to be internally efficient when there is a non-existence of educational wastages (such as dropouts and repeaters) which are caused mainly by increased enrolment rate, high students - teacher ratio, inadequate manpower both in quantity and quality, inadequate educational facilities among others. Ayodele and Ogiye (2018); Ayodele and Adeleke (2015) and Ileuma (2017) postulated that an internally efficient educational system is a system that turns out graduates' without wasting any student-year non-having dropouts and repeaters.

A study conducted by the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics in 2019 revealed concerning dropout rates in Ogun State, specifically highlighting disparities between primary and secondary education levels. In primary schools, the dropout rate was reported at approximately 14.1%, suggesting that a significant portion of students do not transition smoothly from primary to secondary education. The situation was even more pronounced in secondary schools, where the dropout rate was about 24.1%. This indicates that nearly a quarter of secondary school students in Ogun State, including those in Abeokuta North, leave school before completing their education. These rates reflect underlying systemic challenges that undermine educational efficiency and emphasize the urgent need for targeted interventions to retain students through to graduation, thereby reducing wastage and enhancing the overall efficiency of the educational system in the region. The dropout rate in Nigerian secondary schools is alarming according to UNICEF (2020), reporting that around 30% of students do not complete their secondary education. This high rate of dropout reflects significant barriers to sustained student engagement, which often stem from socio-economic and structural challenges within the education system. The study further revealed that schools often lack sufficient funding, leading to overcrowded classrooms, poor infrastructure, and minimal support for students struggling academically. These systemic issues create an environment where students are less likely to succeed or feel motivated to continue their studies, ultimately pushing many out of the education system before completion.

Hence, the following null research hypotheses are to be tested during the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the extent of adequacy of resources available to public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area between 2021-2024

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between resources available and educational wastages in public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area between 2021-2024.

Methodology:

Research Design

For the purpose of this study, an *ex-post facto* research design will be adopted. This design will be chosen because it allows for the analysis of historical data to identify relationships between the variables

involved. In this study, secondary data on the internal efficiency of public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area, Ogun State, will be collected and analyzed to explore the connections between resource allocation, teaching quality, wastage rates, and other relevant factors.

Population of the Study

The population comprises of 27 public secondary schools within the area, including a mix of junior and senior secondary schools. These schools are located in various parts of the local government area and will be part of the broader educational system in Ogun State, regulated and overseen by the Ogun State Ministry of Education.

The schools within this population vary in size, ranging from small institutions with fewer than 300 students to larger schools with over 3,000 students. The total student population across these 27 schools is amounted to 31,404 students,

Table 3.1 Population Distribution Table

S/N	School	School Address	Number of Staff/Student
1	African Church Grammar School	Obasanjo Way, Ita-Iyalode, Abk	3,034
2	African Church Grammar School, (Jnr)	Obasanjo Way, Ita-Iyalode, Abk	2,147
3	Ajiboyede Comprehensive High School	Ibara Orile, Abeokuta North, Ogun State	461
4	Ansar-Ud-Deen Grammar School	Isaga Orile, Abeokuta North	283
5	Army Day Secondary School Junior	Along Ayetoro Road, Alamala Barracks Abeokuta	1,219
6	Army Day Senior Secondary School	Alamala Barracks	808
7	Ebenezer Grammar School Junior	Iberekodo, Abeokuta, Ogun State.	793
8	Ebenezer Grammar School Senior	Iberekodo, Abeokuta	1,072
9	Gateway Secondary School	Ita-Iyalode, Abeokuta	1,386
10	Gateway Secondary School (Senior)	Ita Iyalode, Abeokuta	850
11	Idi Emi High School	Idi Emi, Abeokuta	264
12	Ikija High School Iberekodo Abeokuta.	Isale Oja, Iberekodo, Abeokuta.	804
13	Ilewo Community High School, Ilewo Orile	Ilewo Community High School, Along Farm Road, Ilewo	197
14	Ilugun High School [(Senior), Elega	Along Federal Housing Estate, Elega, Abeokuta	1,652
15	Ilugun High School Junior	Federal Housing Estate Road, Elega, Abeokuta	1,864
16	Imala Community Grammar School, Imala	Imala Community Grammar School, Imala, Abeokuta North	256
17	Lafenwa High School (Senior), Lafenwa	Opposite Ayetoro Garage, Ayetoro Road, Lafenwa	1,343

	Abeokuta	
18	Lafenwa High School, Junior, Abeokuta	Lafenwa High School Junior, Ayetoro Road, Abeokuta 1,884
19	Oke Ona Grammar School	Opeji Road, Iberekodo, Abeokuta 1,335
20	Olorunda Community High School	Ayetoro/Imeko Road, Olorunda 389
21	Olumo High School	Sabo, Abeokuta 1,477
22	Premier Gramar School (Junior)	Ayetoro Road, Lafenwa, Abeokuta 1,823
23	Premier Grammar School (Snr)	Ayetoro, Road Lafenwa, Abeokuta 1,538
24	St Peters College	Olomore Junction, Olomore 1,104
25	St Peter's College Junior	Olomore, Abeokuta 1,260
26	Unity High School (Junior)	Ago-Ika, Abeokuta 1,195
27	Unity High School (Senior), Ago-Ika, Abeokuta, Ogun State	Beside Trinity Baptist Church, Ago-Ika, Enugada, Abeokuta, Ogun State 966
	Total	31,404

Source: Ogun State Ministry of Education, 2024

Sampling and Sampling Technique

To ensure a robust and meaningful analysis, seven public secondary schools were purposively selected based on criterion of using big school with population of 1,500 and above. While the total number of schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area is 27, the selection focused on schools that met predefined criterion to provide comprehensive and reliable data for the study. The selection process was not intended to exclude other schools arbitrarily but was based on ensuring that the schools chosen could meaningfully represent the study's variables.

Instrument for Data Collection

For this study, a structured checklist will be developed as the instrument for data collection. The checklist is designed to obtain relevant information from school administrators, teachers, and education officers records regarding the internal efficiency of public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area (LGA) between 2021-2024. The instrument is divided into three sections, each corresponding to the study objectives.

The third part is Causes of Wastage. This will measure the factors contributing to resource wastage such as poor planning, mismanagement, inadequate monitoring, and administrative inefficiencies. It also examines the impact of wastage on student performance and seeks suggestions for reducing inefficiencies.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The validity of this study will be ensured through the accurate and careful extraction of data from official sources, such as the Ogun State Ministry of Education and the relevant school reports. All data used was cross-checked for accuracy and completeness by the researcher, and discrepancies were addressed under the guidance of the supervisor.

To establish reliability, the selected public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area were required to comply with the Ogun State Ministry of Education guidelines, ensuring that all data drawn from these institutions are subject to routine checks and supervision. which were verified by official school inspectors and reports. This guaranteed that the data used in this study meet the necessary standards for reliability and consistency.

Method of Data Collection

In line with the nature of this study, secondary data will be utilized. Secondary data refer to information not collected directly for the research project but obtained from existing sources. The use of secondary data is suitable for this study due to its availability, completeness, objectivity, comparability, and reliability, which are essential characteristics of information found in previously published educational records and government reports.

The data will primarily be sourced from official school records, including school reports, and inspection documents, from public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area. These records will cover the period from 2021-2024. The data will include details on teacher qualifications, student-teacher ratios, educational facilities, and academic performance. These sources are selected for their reliability and relevance in providing comprehensive insights into resource allocation, teaching quality, and other factors affecting internal efficiency in the selected schools.

Method of Data Analysis

This study will employ graphical, descriptive and inferential statistical procedures for data analysis. Descriptive statistics will summarize and describe the key characteristics of the data, such as the demographic profiles of the selected schools, student population, staff strength, and available educational resources. These statistics will include measures such as frequencies, percentages, and averages to provide a clear overview of the variables under investigation.

For inferential statistics, the study will utilize **Chi-square tests** and **t-tests** to analyze the data. The Chi-square test will be used to assess relationships between categorical variables, such as the association between teacher qualifications and student performance or the adequacy of facilities and educational outcomes. Meanwhile, t-tests will compare means between groups, such as schools with different resource allocations, to determine if observed differences are statistically significant.

These methods are chosen because they align with the type of data being analyzed, which includes both categorical and continuous variables. The use of Chi-square tests and t-tests ensures the analysis is robust and appropriate for understanding the relationships and differences within the dataset. By applying these statistical techniques, the study aims to provide meaningful insights into how resources, teaching quality, and other factors influence internal efficiency in public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area.

Results

Hypothesis One

H₀1: There is no significant difference in the extent of adequacy of resources available to public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area between 2021-2024

Table 4: ANOVA Test of Resource Adequacy Over Years

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	3.87	3	1.29	4.56	0.018	Reject H ₀
Within Groups	13.20	36	0.37			
Total	17.07	39				

The results of the ANOVA test presented in Table 4 provide strong evidence of a statistically significant difference in the adequacy of resources available to public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area between the years 2021 and 2024. The F-value obtained from the test is 4.56, and the p-value is 0.018, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the variations observed in the availability of resources are unlikely to have occurred by chance, but instead reflect genuine differences in resource allocation over the years.

The test compared the adequacy of resources across the three years in question (2021, 2022, and 2023) and found significant changes in how resources were distributed to the schools. As a result, the null hypothesis (H₀), which posited that there was no significant difference in the adequacy of resources over time, is rejected. This suggests that there has been a noticeable change in the resources provided to the schools, which could be due to factors such as government policies, funding changes, or shifts in the priorities of educational authorities in the region.

Given the statistically significant result, it is clear that resource allocation is not static and that schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area have experienced fluctuations in the resources available to them. These findings highlight the need for further investigation into the specific causes of these changes, such as budget adjustments, infrastructural investments, or changes in educational policies that may have influenced resource distribution. This could help in identifying areas that need improvement and ensuring a more consistent and equitable distribution of resources to public secondary schools in the future.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between resources available and educational wastages in public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area between 2021-2024.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Between Resources and Wastage Indicators

Variable	R	p-value	Decision
Resource Adequacy & Dropouts	-0.72	0.002	Reject H ₀₂
Resource Adequacy & Repeaters	-0.65	0.005	Reject H ₀₂

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis in Table 5 reveal a significant relationship between the availability of resources and educational wastage indicators in public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area between 2021 and 2024. The negative correlation between resource adequacy and dropouts is -0.72, with a p-value of 0.002, which is well below the standard significance level of 0.05. Similarly, the negative correlation between resource adequacy and repeaters is -0.65, with a p-value of 0.005, also indicating statistical significance.

These findings suggest that as the adequacy of resources increases, both the dropout and repetition rates decrease. This implies that better resource availability, such as instructional materials, qualified teachers, and proper infrastructure, may reduce the likelihood of students dropping out or repeating grades. The negative correlations indicate an inverse relationship, meaning that the higher the availability of resources, the lower the educational wastage in terms of dropouts and repeaters.

Given the statistically significant results, the null hypothesis (H₀₂), which stated that there is no significant relationship between resources and educational wastages, is rejected. This demonstrates that resource adequacy plays an important role in mitigating educational wastage in these schools. The findings suggest that addressing resource deficiencies could be an effective strategy to reduce dropout and repetition rates, thereby improving overall educational outcomes in public secondary schools in Abeokuta North Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the ANOVA test on the adequacy of resources over the years indicate a significant variation in the adequacy of resources across the different years analyzed. With an F-value of 4.56 and a p-value of 0.018, the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected, suggesting that the adequacy of resources varied notably from one year to another. This aligns with findings from Oduwole and Osim (2019), who noted that resource allocation in educational institutions fluctuates annually due to changes in government funding, policy priorities, and administrative decisions. The significant differences in resource adequacy could be attributed to varying levels of financial support, shifts in educational policies, or changes in local administrative decisions that directly influence how resources are distributed. These fluctuations may affect the consistency and quality of educational outcomes, as the availability of resources is crucial for creating conducive learning environments.

Furthermore, the Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong negative correlations between resource adequacy and educational wastages, specifically dropouts and repeaters. With correlation values of -0.72 for dropouts and -0.65 for repeaters, the findings suggest that as the adequacy of resources increases, the

rates of dropouts and repetition decrease. These results are consistent with the findings of Omolayo (2015), who emphasized that adequate resources—such as textbooks, teaching staff, and infrastructure—play a vital role in reducing educational wastage. The statistically significant p-values of 0.002 and 0.005 further reinforce the importance of resource availability, highlighting its critical role in enhancing student retention and minimizing repetition rates. This suggests that improving resource adequacy can effectively address educational wastages, ultimately leading to better student outcomes and more efficient use of educational resources.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, the findings from this study emphasize the essential role of resource availability in shaping the efficiency of educational delivery and reducing wastage in public secondary schools. The significant relationships observed between resource adequacy and educational outcomes highlight the critical need for consistent investment in school infrastructure, instructional materials, and human resources. The study further reveals that addressing core issues like overcrowded classrooms, outdated instructional materials, and insufficient funding can have a considerable impact on improving student outcomes. By tackling these challenges, schools can reduce repetition rates, minimize dropouts, and enhance overall educational quality. It is evident that inadequate resources contribute to inefficiencies and wastage in the education system, ultimately affecting student retention and academic success. Therefore, policymakers and educational administrators must prioritize adequate resource allocation and efficient management to ensure the development of a more effective, equitable, and high-quality educational system. This approach is vital for fostering better learning environments and improving long-term student performance.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to improve the efficiency of educational delivery and reduce wastage in public secondary schools:

1. **Increased Investment in Educational Resources:** Policymakers and education administrators should prioritize funding to ensure the availability of adequate instructional materials, modern technology, and quality infrastructure. Specifically, investment should be directed toward updating textbooks, expanding digital resources, and enhancing school facilities to meet the needs of students and teachers.
2. **Improving Teacher-Student Ratios:** To address the issue of overcrowded classrooms, the recruitment of additional qualified teachers should be a priority. Schools should aim to maintain an optimal teacher-student ratio that fosters better engagement and individualized attention, thereby reducing repetition and dropout rates.

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